

Pedagogical Approach of Teachers As Determinant of Learning Interest of Students in Public Secondary Schools

Thellemae B. Alcantara

Abstract. The research explored how pedagogical approaches influence students' learning interests in public secondary schools. The study involved 190 Grade 7-10 students from public secondary schools in San Isidro South District in Davao Oriental as respondents, selected using the stratified random sampling technique. It employed a non-experimental quantitative research design, precisely the descriptive-correlational method. Statistical analysis was conducted using Mean, Pearson Product Moment Correlation, and Linear Regression Analysis on the collected data. Findings revealed that the pedagogical approach to students' learning interest in public secondary schools in San Isidro South District in Davao Oriental was described as moderately extensive. Further, correlation analysis demonstrated a significant relationship between the pedagogical approach and students' learning interest in public secondary schools in San Isidro South District in Davao Oriental. Evidently, regression analysis proved that the pedagogical approach in terms of engagement through interactive learning, relevance to real-world applications, and personalized learning experiences were significant predictors of students' learning interest in public secondary schools in San Isidro South District in Davao Oriental. The researcher recommends that the Department of Education should encourage curriculum flexibility to allow teachers to adapt pedagogical approaches to students' specific needs and interests. The study, therefore, was conducted further to utilize findings through publication in a reputable research journal.

KEY WORDS

1. educational management 2. pedagogical approach 3. learning interest

Date Received: October 05, 2024 — Date Reviewed: November 10, 2024 — Date Published: December 10, 2024

1. Introduction

Understanding the influence of pedagogical approaches on the learning interest of students was critical in enhancing educational outcomes and fostering a lifelong love for learning. Effective teaching strategies were essential for engaging students and motivating them to actively participate in their educational journey. However, there was a notable gap in the existing literature, particularly in quantitative studies that provided empirical evidence on this relationship. Additionally, the unique cultural and educational contexts of different regions, such as the Philippines, necessitated localized research to develop contextually relevant educational practices. Conducting this study provided valuable insights into how specific pedagogical methods could be tailored to boost student interest and engagement, ultimately leading to im-

proved academic performance and satisfaction. In the United States, a significant issue contributing to the lack of learning interest among secondary school students is the overemphasis on standardized testing. The pressure to perform well on these tests often leads to a narrowing of the curriculum, where teachers focus more on test preparation rather than fostering a deeper understanding and love for learning (Nichols Berliner, 2019). This environment can stifle creativity and critical thinking, making learning feel more like a chore than an engaging process. Additionally, socio-economic disparities contribute to differences in educational experiences, where students from underprivileged backgrounds may lack access to enriching educational resources, further diminishing their interest in school (Reardon, 2019). In many Asian countries, the highly competitive educational systems and cultural emphasis on academic achievement can create significant stress and pressure on students, leading to a decline in learning interest. The rigorous and often rote-learning-focused education systems in countries like China, Japan, and South Korea prioritize exam results over creative and critical thinking (Li Zhou, 2019). This can result in students experiencing burnout and disengagement from learning at an early age. Furthermore, the societal and parental expectations for high academic performance can lead to a lack of balance between academic pursuits and extracurricular activities, reducing overall student motivation and interest in learning (Chen, 2019). In Arabian countries, the lack of learning interest among secondary school students can be attributed to traditional teaching methods and limited access to modern educational resources. Many schools in this region still rely heavily on lecture-based instruction, which can be disengaging for students accustomed to interactive and technology-enhanced learning environments (Almulla, 2020). Additionally, cultural factors and gender disparities in education can impact students' interest in learning. For example, girls in some Arabian countries may face societal restrictions that limit their educational opportunities, affecting their motivation and engagement (Elamin, 2019). Moreover, the rapid socio-economic changes in the region demand an education system that can adapt and provide relevant skills, yet many schools struggle to keep pace with these changes, leading to outdated curricula that fail to capture students' interest. One of the primary issues contributing to the lack of learning interest among secondary school students in the Philippines is the traditional, lecture-based approach to teaching, which often fails to engage students actively. According to Corpuz and Salandanan (2020), many schools continue to rely heavily on rote memorization and standardized testing, which do not stimulate critical thinking or creativity. This method of instruction can lead to student disengagement and a lack of motivation, as it does not cater to the diverse learning styles and interests of students. Additionally, the overcrowded classrooms and high student-to-teacher ratios prevalent in many public schools further exacerbate this problem, making it difficult for teachers to provide individualized attention and support to students (Salandanan, 2020). Another significant challenge is the lack of resources and extracurricular activities that can enhance the learning experience and make education more appealing to students. Many schools in the Philippines, especially in rural areas, suffer from inadequate facilities, limited access to technology, and insufficient teaching materials (Pangilinan, 2019). These resource constraints hinder the ability of teachers to implement interactive and engaging teaching methods that could spark students' interest in learning. Furthermore, the pressure to excel in national exams and the high-stakes nature of the Philippine education system can lead to increased stress and anxiety among students, detracting from their natural curiosity and enthusiasm for

learning (Bernardo, 2019). Despite the extensive literature highlighting the importance of pedagogical approaches in enhancing students' learning interest, there is a notable scarcity of quantitative research in this area. Most existing studies predominantly employ qualitative methodologies such as interviews, case studies, and classroom observations, which provide rich, descriptive insights but lack the statistical rigor needed for broader generalizations. Quantitative research is crucial for establishing empirical evidence on the specific impacts of different pedagogical strategies on student engagement and interest. Such data-driven studies can offer more precise measurements and predictive insights, thereby informing best practices and educational policies. The lack of quantitative approaches leaves a significant gap in understanding how pedagogical methods quantitatively influence learning interest, highlighting the urgent need for robust statistical research

in this domain. Moreover, the researcher has not yet encountered any studies specifically examining this relationship within the Philippine context, particularly in San Isidro South District, Davao Oriental. The unique cultural and educational dynamics of the Philippines necessitate localized research to understand how various teaching strategies impact student interest and engagement in this specific setting. Conducting this study in the Philippines is crucial as it will provide contextually relevant insights that can inform local educational practices and policies. The findings from such a study can help educators in San Isidro South District and similar regions develop more effective pedagogical approaches tailored to their students' needs, ultimately enhancing learning outcomes. Addressing this research gap is imperative to improve the quality of education and student engagement in the Philippines, making this study both timely and essential.

2. Methodology

This section contains the research design, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—In this study, the researcher utilized a quantitative research approach, precisely the descriptive-correlational technique, to gather data, ideas, facts, and information related to the study. As characterized by Creswell and Creswell (2018), methodologies and strategies were employed to systematically and impartially gather and scrutinize numerical data, aiming to comprehend phenomena, correlations, or trends. These methods entailed employing statistical analysis to extract insights and make deductions from the data. Quantitative research involves the collection and analysis of numerical data to examine various aspects of phenomena, relationships, or patterns within a structured framework. This type of research relied heavily on quantifiable measures and sta-

tistical techniques to draw objective conclusions based on empirical evidence. Researchers often employed surveys, experiments, or observational studies to gather data, which was then subjected to statistical analysis to identify trends, correlations, or significant differences. On one hand, McCombes (2019) defined descriptive research techniques as strategies that involved methods utilized to depict, observe, and analyze the characteristics, behaviors, or phenomena of interest without exerting influence or manipulation. The primary objective was to offer a comprehensive portrayal of the subject being studied, prioritizing the depiction of existing conditions rather than delving into causality. Descriptive research typically employs a range of observational approaches, sur-

veys, case studies, and archival investigations. Additionally, descriptive research enabled researchers to delineate and characterize various attributes, traits, or features of a population, group, or phenomenon, including demographic particulars, behaviors, attitudes, and other pertinent factors. On the other hand, Privitera (2020) characterized correlational research design as a form of non-experimental research employed to investigate the connection between two or more variables. This method entailed gauging the degree to which alterations in one variable corresponded with alterations in another, without manipulating either variable. The aim was to ascertain whether there existed a statistical correlation between the variables and to discern the direction and magnitude of this association. Correlational research served as a vital tool in advancing knowledge across diverse domains by unveiling relationships between variables, generating hypotheses, and informing practical applications and interventions. Despite the limitations inherent in correlational studies, such as the inability to establish causality, they furnished valuable insights that complemented experimental research endeavors and enriched our comprehension of intricate phenomena. Using a quantitative descriptive correlational research design was highly appropriate for studying the influence of pedagogical approaches of teachers on students' learning interests. This design allowed researchers to systematically measure and analyze the relationships between variables using statistical techniques, providing empirical evidence on how different teaching methods impacted students' engagement and motivation. By collecting numerical data through surveys or assessments, researchers could quantify the degree of association between pedagogical strategies and learning interest, offering a clear understanding of which approaches were most effective. Additionally, this design supported the objective examination of large sample sizes, enhancing the generalizability of the findings

to broader populations. The quantitative descriptive correlational approach was particularly useful for identifying trends and patterns that could inform educational practices and policies, making it a robust method for exploring this educational dynamic.

2.2. Research Respondents—The respondents of the study were junior high school students in San Isidro South District, Davao Oriental. The sample size for the selection of the respondents was 190, which was taken from the approximately 450 total numbers of teachers in the schools in San Isidro South District, Davao Oriental. The sample size was computed and obtained through the use of the Sloving formula for the sample size. The use of Slovin's formula is appropriate because the sample is taken from a large population and there is a need to take into account confidence levels and margins of error. Moreover, a stratified random sampling technique was utilized in the selection of the 300 respondents in this study. According to Pandey (2015) stratified random sampling is a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata. In stratified random sampling or stratification, the strata are formed based on members' shared attributes or characteristics, such as income or educational attainment. Stratified random sampling is appropriate in this study because there is heterogeneity in a population that can be classified with ancillary information. In this study, certain inclusion criteria were implemented in determining the respondents of the study. The primary consideration of this study was to choose respondents who could provide information to achieve the purpose of this study. The inclusion criteria are as follows: students who are currently enrolled in public secondary schools, excluding private or other types of institutions, and students who voluntarily signed the ICF and parental consent were given the survey questionnaires. Moreover, the study was delimited only to the nature of the problem based on

the research questions, and thus, it did not consider the socioeconomic status of the students in public secondary schools.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—The study used adapted and modified survey questionnaires to suit the current investigation. The first part is about the pedagogical approach, which is composed of and was divided into the domains, namely, engagement through interactive learning, relevance to real-world applications, personalized learning experiences, and cultural and contextual relevance. The reliability of the scale

was determined to be very high, as indicated by a Cronbach’s alpha value of 0.954. This value falls within the ”excellent” range, suggesting that the scale consistently measures the intended construct. Consequently, the results obtained from this scale can be considered both reliable and dependable for further analysis. As a guide in determining the extent of the pedagogical approach, the researcher used a range of means, descriptions and interpretations as presented below:

Range of Mean, Descriptive Level, and Interpretation

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The pedagogical approach is always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The pedagogical approach is oftentimes observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The pedagogical approach is sometimes observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The pedagogical approach is seldom observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The pedagogical approach is never observed.

The second part of the instrument was about the learning interests of students in the San Isidro South District in Davao Oriental. This questionnaire was a researcher-made indicated with student-centered learning, technology integration, experiential learning, and formative assessment. The questionnaire underwent a reliability test and obtained a Cronbach’s alpha value of 0.978, which is interpreted as excellent. This high alpha value indicates that the ques-

tionnaire has a very high level of internal consistency, meaning that the items within the questionnaire reliably measure the same underlying construct. As a result, the data collected from this questionnaire can be considered highly reliable for the purposes of the study. As a guide in determining the extent of learning interest, the researcher made use of the range of means, descriptions and interpretations as presented below:

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—Steps were undergone by the researcher in conducting the study after the validation of the research questionnaire. Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher secured the permission to conduct the study. The researcher secured

the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City. The endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City, was attached to the permission letters to be endorsed to the

Range of Mean, Descriptive Level, and Interpretation

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The pedagogical approach is always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The pedagogical approach is oftentimes observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The pedagogical approach is sometimes observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The pedagogical approach is seldom observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The pedagogical approach is never observed.

schools division superintendent and then to the school principals of the selected elementary public schools in San Isidro South District, Davao Oriental. Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. The researcher proceeded to distribute the research instrument to the respondents after the approval to conduct the study. The study was conducted last October 10-12, 2023. Upon the distribution of the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey were briefly discussed and explained to the identified respon-

dents of the study. For the administration of the questionnaire, the respondents of the study were given enough testing time for the questionnaires to be finished. After this, the data collected were subjected to quantitative analysis. Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data. After the questionnaire was retrieved, the scores of each respondent were tallied to organize the data per indicator. After that, each score was subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data: Mean. Mean was useful in characterizing the pedagogical approach and learning interests of students in public secondary schools in San Isidro South District, Davao Oriental. Mean is descriptive statistics that tend to measure how the scores cluster. It was used to supply answers to objectives 1 and 2. Pearson Product Moment Correlation. This was utilized to determine the signif-

icance of the relationship between the pedagogical approach and the learning interest of students in public secondary schools in San Isidro South District, Davao Oriental. It is a statistical measure of the strength of a linear relationship between paired data. This was used to supply answers to objective 3. Linear Regression Analysis. It was applied to evaluate the significance of which domains of independent (pedagogical approach) variable significantly influence the dependent (learning interest of students). This was used to supply answers to objective 4.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It was sequenced based on the objectives of the study as presented in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extent of the pedagogical approach and the learning interest of students; the significant relationship between the

pedagogical approach and the learning interest of students; and the influence of the pedagogical approach on the learning interest of students

Table 1 shows the summary of the pedagogical approach of teachers in San Isidro South District, Davao Oriental. It shows that the overall mean of the pedagogical approach of teachers is 3.27, which is described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed. The result highlights the importance of striking a balance between traditional and innovative teaching methods. This balance is crucial for creating a dynamic and adaptable learning environment where both teachers and students can

thrive. Bijlsma et al. (2019) observed that moderate levels of pedagogical approaches in teaching strike a vital balance between traditional and innovative methods, fostering a dynamic and adaptable learning environment. This balanced approach enables teachers to integrate new strategies, such as student-centered learning and technology use, without overwhelming themselves or their students with constant changes.

Table 1. Summary of Pedagogical Approach in San Isidro South District, Davao Oriental

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Engagement through Interactive Learning	3.51	Extensive
Relevance to Real-World Applications	3.21	Moderately Extensive
Personalized Learning Experiences	3.23	Moderately Extensive
Cultural and Contextual Relevance	3.11	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.27	Moderately Extensive

Moreover, the result emphasizes that student engagement is a key factor in creating a productive classroom environment. In a moderately extensive pedagogical approach, when teachers effectively engage students, it leads to increased attentiveness, curiosity, and motivation to explore new ideas. Toba et al. (2019) stated that when students are engaged, they tend to be more attentive, curious, and motivated to explore new ideas, which leads to a more dynamic and productive classroom atmosphere.

Table 2 is the summary on the extent of learning interest of students in public secondary schools in San Isidro South District, Davao Oriental. As shown in the table, learning in-

terest of students in San Isidro South District, Davao Oriental obtained an overall mean score of 3.32 with a moderately extensive descriptive rating and interpreted as sometimes manifested by the students. In the context of moderately extensive learning interest, the balanced level of student interest is essential for sustaining engagement without leading to burnout or anxiety. Students who exhibit moderate interest are motivated enough to engage meaningfully in their educational activities, contributing to classroom discussions, and diligently completing assignments. This level of interest ensures that students remain focused and involved without the pressure of excessive fixation, leading to a

healthier and more productive learning environment. This aligns with Febriyanti and Putra's (2020) assertion that moderate levels of learning interest are crucial for maintaining consistent student engagement. They offer a balanced and sustainable way for students to involve them-

selves in educational activities. Students with moderate interest are adequately motivated to actively participate in class discussions, complete their assignments, and interact with learning materials without becoming overly obsessive or stressed.

Table 2. Summary of Learning Interest of Students in Public Secondary Schools in San Isidro South District, Davao Oriental

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Confidence	3.23	Moderately Extensive
Collaboration	3.34	Moderately Extensive
Time Consciousness	3.32	Moderately Extensive
Self-Discipline	3.38	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.32	Moderately Extensive

Moderately extensive learning interest significantly influences teaching practices by fostering deeper engagement and improved learning outcomes. When students have a genuine interest in the subjects they are studying, they are more likely to delve deeply into the material, leading to enhanced understanding and retention of information. Teachers who recognize and incorporate students' interests into their lesson plans can create more engaging and relatable educational experiences. According to Prasetyo and Riyanto (2019), the significance of learning interest to teaching practices is substantial, as students who show genuine interest in their studies are more inclined to engage deeply with the material, resulting in better comprehension and retention. When teachers connect with students' interests, they can design lessons that are more engaging and relevant. Relationship Between Pedagogical Approach and Learning Interests of Students in Public Secondary

Schools in San Isidro South District, Davao Oriental

The results of the analysis of the relationship between the pedagogical approach and the learning interest of students in public secondary schools in San Isidro South District in Davao Oriental are presented. Bivariate correlation analysis using Pearson Product Moment Correlation was utilized to determine the relationship between the variables mentioned. Table 3 shows that the pedagogical approach has a significant positive relationship with the learning interest of students in public secondary schools in San Isidro South District in Davao Oriental with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .802, p < 0.05$). It means that as the extent of the pedagogical approach changes, the extent of learning interest of students in public secondary schools also significantly changes.

Table 3. Relationship Between Pedagogical Approach and Learning Interest of Students in Public Secondary Schools in San Isidro South District, Davao Oriental

Pedagogical Approach	r-value	p-value	Decision
Engagement through Interactive Learning	0.872*	0.000	Reject H0
Relevance to Real-World Applications	0.831*	0.000	Reject H0
Personalized Learning Experiences	0.771*	0.000	Reject H0
Cultural and Contextual Relevance	0.776*	0.000	Reject H0
Overall Pedagogical Approach	0.802*	0.000	Reject H0

*Significant @ $p < 0.05$.

The findings align with Anders and Evans' (2019) perspective that interactive learning approaches emphasize active student involvement in the educational process, transforming them from passive recipients to co-creators of knowledge. Student-centered learning addresses the needs, interests, and learning styles of students, making the educational experience more engaging and relevant. When students recognize the connection between their learning and their personal lives or future aspirations, their interest in the subject matter grows, resulting in increased motivation and participation in classroom activities. Moreover, the table also shows that pedagogical approach in terms of learner empowerment; self-directed learning; active learning engagement; and technology integration are significantly correlated with learning interest of students in public secondary schools with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .872, p < 0.05$), ($r = .831, p < 0.05$), ($r = .771, p < 0.05$), and ($r = .776, p < 0.05$), respectively. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between pedagogical approach and learning interest of students in public secondary schools in San Isidro South District in

Davao Oriental. Additionally, creating a supportive and interactive learning environment is crucial for enhancing students' interest. Teachers who cultivate a positive classroom climate, encourage collaborative learning, and use interactive technologies can significantly boost student engagement and interest. This supports Toropova et al.'s (2019) idea that fostering a supportive and interactive learning environment is another key element of pedagogical strategies that enhance students' learning interests. Teachers who create a positive classroom atmosphere, promote collaboration, and incorporate interactive technologies can significantly increase students' interest and engagement. Influence of Pedagogical Approach on the Learning Interest of Students in Public Secondary Schools in San Isidro South District, Davao Oriental

Table 4 shows the results of the regression analysis. In a singular capacity, the pedagogical approach in terms of engagement through interactive learning significantly influenced the learning interest of students with a p-value that is less than the .05 level of significance (2-tailed) ($p < .05$) with a positive unstandardized beta value of .376. It means that for every unit increase in the value of the extent of pedagogical approach in

terms of engagement through interactive learning, there is a corresponding increase of .376 in the extent of learning interest of students.

Table 4. Influence of Pedagogical Approach on the Learning Interest of Students in Public Secondary Schools in San Isidro South District, Davao Oriental

Pedagogical Approach	B	p-value	Decision
Engagement through Interactive Learning	0.376*	0.000	Reject H0
Relevance to Real-World Applications	0.201*	0.000	Reject H0
Personalized Learning Experiences	0.124*	0.001	Reject H0
Cultural and Contextual Relevance	-0.046	0.080	Accept H0

R² = 0.334 **F-value = 102.114****
p-value = 0.000

*Significant @ p<0.05; **Significant F-value.

As proposed by Qureshi et al. (2023), employing interactive learning techniques like group discussions, practical activities, and digital tools creates a more engaging and participatory classroom atmosphere. This method not only grabs students' attention but also motivates them to take an active part in their education. Studies show that when students engage in interactive learning, their interest and excitement for the subject matter grow, resulting in enhanced cognitive engagement and better knowledge retention. Further, in singular capacity, pedagogical approach in terms of relevance to real-world applications significantly influenced the learning interest of students with a p-value that is less than the .05 level of significance (2-tailed) (p<.05) with a positive beta value of .201. It means that for every unit increase in the extent of pedagogical approach in terms of relevance to real-world applications, there is a corresponding increase of .201 in the extent of learning interest of students. This aligns with Morley

and Jamil's (2021) claim that students' motivation to understand and apply concepts rises when they recognize the practical implications of their learning. Connecting educational content to real-world scenarios enables students to appreciate the value of their education and its applicability beyond the classroom, thereby fostering a deeper and more sustained interest in the subject matter. Furthermore, in singular capacity, pedagogical approach in terms of personalized learning experiences significantly influenced the learning interest of students with a p-value that is less than the .05 level of significance (2-tailed) (p<.05) with a positive beta value of .124. It means that for every unit increase in the extent of pedagogical approach in terms of personalized learning experiences, there is a corresponding increase of .124 in the extent of learning interest of students. The findings align with Bernacki et al. (2021), who stated that personalized learning experiences significantly enhance students' learning interest

by customizing educational content and activities to suit their individual needs, preferences, and learning styles. When students recognize that their personal interests and needs are being considered, they are more likely to feel valued and motivated to actively engage in their education. Personalized learning nurtures a sense of ownership over the learning process, motivating students to set personal goals and pursue them with greater enthusiasm and dedication. Significantly, of the three domains, engagement through interactive learning had a greater impact on learning beliefs of students than relevance to real-world applications and personalized learning experiences. Additionally, the combined influence of the domains of pedagogical approach towards the learning beliefs of students is significant ($F = 102.114$, $p < 0.05$). Meanwhile, the model explains 33.40 percent of the variance of the learning interest of students based on the independent variable explored in this study as indicated by $R^2 = .334$. This means

that 66.60 percent of the variance of the learning interest of students can be attributed to other factors aside from the pedagogical approach. In conducting this research, it is crucial to evaluate the extent to which the empirical data either corroborates or contradicts the underlying theoretical assumptions. Experiential Learning Theory by Kolb (1984) provides valuable insights into how the pedagogical approaches of teachers can significantly influence students' learning interest. By emphasizing a learning process that involves concrete experiences, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization, and active experimentation, teachers can create dynamic and engaging learning environments. This method caters to students' natural curiosity and need for real-world application of knowledge, thereby boosting their intrinsic motivation to learn. When teachers incorporate hands-on activities and encourage reflection and experimentation, they foster deeper cognitive engagement and a stronger connection to the material.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the researcher's conclusions and recommendations. The discussions were supported by the literature presented in the first chapters, and the conclusion were in accordance with statements of the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—The primary objective of this study was to evaluate which domains of pedagogical approach significantly influence the learning interest of students in public secondary schools utilizing a non-experimental quantitative design using a descriptive-correlation technique. The researcher selected the 190 Grade 7-10 students in San Isidro South District, Division of Davao Oriental, as the respondents through a stratified random sampling method. The researcher made use of modified and enhanced adapted survey questionnaires, which were pilot-tested in a nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consistency of the items in the instrument. Pedagogical approach

in public secondary schools in San Isidro South District, Davao Oriental got an overall mean of 3.27 with a moderately extensive descriptive rating. Also, the pedagogical approach in terms of engagement through interactive learning, relevance to real-world applications, personalized learning experiences, and cultural and contextual relevance obtained the mean scores of 3.51, 3.21, 3.23, and 3.11, respectively. The learning interest of students in public secondary schools in San Isidro South District in Davao Oriental has an overall mean of 3.32 and a moderately extensive descriptive rating. Also, students' learning interest in terms of student-centered learning, technology integration, ex-

periential learning, and formative assessment obtained mean scores of 3.23, 3.34, 3.34, 3.32, and 3.38, respectively. In addition, the result showed that the pedagogical approach has a significant positive relationship with the learning interest of students in public secondary schools in San Isidro South District in Davao Oriental with a p-value of .000, which is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .802$, $p < 0.05$). This means that as the pedagogical approach changes, students' learning interest in public secondary schools in San Isidro South District in Davao Oriental also changes significantly. Overall, the pedagogical approach significantly influences the learning interest of students in public secondary schools in San Isidro South District in Davao Oriental, as evidenced by the F-value of 102.114 and $p < 0.05$. The r^2 value of 0.334 indicated that the pedagogical approach has contributed significantly to the variability of the learning interest of students in public secondary schools by 33.40% of the total variability. Moreover, pedagogical approach in terms of engagement through interactive learning, relevance to real-world applications, and personalized learning experiences were significant predictors of students' learning interest as indicated by the regression coefficient values of 0.376, 0.201, and 0.124, respectively.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study several conclusions were generated: The pedagogical approach in public secondary schools in San Isidro South District in Davao Oriental was moderately extensive. The findings underscore the significance of balancing traditional and innovative teaching methods. Achieving this balance was essential for fostering a dynamic and adaptable learning environment where educators and students can excel. Bijlsma et al. (2019) noted that moderate levels of pedagogical approaches in teaching effectively blend traditional and innovative methods, creating a vibrant and flexible learning atmosphere. This balanced strategy allows teachers

to incorporate new techniques, such as student-centered learning and technology integration, without overwhelming themselves or their students with continuous changes. The learning interest of students in public secondary schools in San Isidro South District in Davao Oriental was rated as moderately extensive. This supports Febriyanti and Putra's (2020) claim that moderate levels of learning interest are essential for sustaining consistent student engagement, providing a balanced and manageable way for students to participate in educational activities. Students with a moderate level of interest are sufficiently motivated to engage in class discussions, complete their assignments, and interact with learning materials without becoming overly obsessive or stressed. The result showed pedagogical approach has a significant positive relationship with students' learning interest in public secondary schools in San Isidro South District in Davao Oriental. The findings are consistent with Anders and Evans' (2019) view that interactive learning approaches focus on active student involvement in the educational process, turning them from passive recipients into active co-creators of knowledge. Student-centered learning addresses students' needs, interests, and learning styles, making the educational experience more engaging and relevant. When students see the connection between their learning and their personal lives or future aspirations, their interest in the subject increases, leading to higher motivation and participation in classroom activities. The findings were consistent with Anders and Evans' (2019) view that interactive learning approaches focus on active student involvement in the educational process, turning them from passive recipients into active co-creators of knowledge. Student-centered learning addresses students' needs, interests, and learning styles, making the educational experience more engaging and relevant. When students see the connection between their learning and their personal lives or future aspirations,

their interest in the subject matter increases, leading to higher motivation and participation in classroom activities

4.3. *Recommendations*—Based on the findings and conclusions generated from the study, the researcher recommends the following: Department of Education may encourage curriculum flexibility to allow teachers to adapt pedagogical approaches to students' specific needs and interests. DepEd may invest in teacher training and professional development programs that focus on innovative pedagogical methods to enhance student learning interest. School heads may empower teachers to experiment with and adapt pedagogical approaches based on student's interests, needs, and feedback. Adding more, they may establish mechanisms for collecting feedback from students about their learning experiences, which could inform adjustments to pedagogical approaches. Teachers may prioritize student-centered peda-

gogical approaches that allow students to take an active role in their learning and pursue topics of interest. More so, differentiate instruction to accommodate varying learning interests, abilities, and learning styles among students. Students may take an active role in their education by expressing their interests, asking questions, and providing feedback on the learning methods that work best for them. Additionally, they may develop effective time management and study skills to balance their interests with academic responsibilities. Future researchers may conduct both quantitative and qualitative research to gain a comprehensive understanding of the impact of pedagogical approaches. They may conduct further analysis on other factors that improve students' learning interest in public secondary schools in San Isidro South District in Davao Oriental since the pedagogical approach only contributed 32.70

5. References

- Abugohar, M. A., Yunus, K., & Ab Rashid, R. (2019). Smartphone applications as a teaching technique for enhancing tertiary learners' speaking skills: Perceptions and practices. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (Online)*, 14(9), 74.
- Adelson, J. L. (2019). Educational research with real-world data: Reducing selection bias with propensity score analysis. *Practical Assessment, Research, and Evaluation*, 18(1), 15. <https://scholarworks.umass.edu/pare/vol18/iss1/15/>
- Agustini, K., Wahyuni, D. S., Mertayasa, I. N. E., Wedhanti, N. K., & Sukrawarpala, W. (2021). Student-centered learning models and learning outcomes: Meta-analysis and effect sizes on the students' thesis. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1810(1), 012049. <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1742-6596/1810/1/012049/meta>
- Alamri, H., Lowell, V., Watson, W., & Watson, S. L. (2020). Using personalized learning as an instructional approach to motivate learners in online higher education: Learner self-determination and intrinsic motivation. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 52(3), 322–352.
- Almulla, M. (2020). Implementing a flipped classroom model in the arabian gulf: A study of secondary school teachers' perceptions and practices. *International Journal of Education and Development using Information and Communication Technology*, 16(1), 60–79.
- Anders, P. L., & Evans, K. S. (2019). Relationship between teachers' beliefs and their instructional practice in reading. In *Beliefs about text and instruction with text* (pp. 137–153). Routledge.

- <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/edit/10.4324/9780203812068-8/relationship-teachers-beliefs-instructional-practice-reading-patricia-anders-karen-evans>
- Apriani, R. (2019). The effect of learning media and interest in learning on english learning outcomes. *English Journal*, 13(2), 68–78. <https://ejournal.uika-bogor.ac.id/index.php/ENGLISH/article/view/3780>
- Arnesen, K. T., Graham, C. R., Short, C. R., & Archibald, D. (2019). Experiences with personalized learning in a blended teaching course for preservice teachers. *Journal of Online Learning Research*, 5(3), 275–310.
- Aytaç, T., & Kula, S. S. (2020). The effect of student-centered approaches on students' creative thinking skills: A meta-analysis study. *International Journal of Contemporary Educational Research*, 7(2), 62–80. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1285436>
- Backfisch, I., Lachner, A., Stürmer, K., & Scheiter, K. (2021a). Variability of teachers' technology integration in the classroom: A matter of utility! *Computers & Education*, 166, 104159.
- Backfisch, I., Lachner, A., Stürmer, K., & Scheiter, K. (2021b). Variability of teachers' technology integration in the classroom: A matter of utility! *Computers Education*, 166, 104159.
- Benlahcene, A., Lashari, S. A., Lashari, T. A., Shehzad, M. W., & Deli, W. (2020). Exploring the perception of students using student-centered learning approach in a malaysian public university. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 9(1), 204–217. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1240462>
- Bernacki, M. L., Greene, M. J., & Lobczowski, N. G. (2021). A systematic review of research on personalized learning: Personalized by whom, to what, how, and for what purpose(s)? *Educational Psychology Review*, 33(4), 1675–1715.
- Cao, Y., Postareff, L., Lindblom-Ylänne, S., & Toom, A. (2023). A survey research on finnish teacher educators' research-teaching integration and its relationship with their approaches to teaching. *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 46(1), 171–198.
- Cennamo, K., & Kalk, D. (2019). *Real world instructional design: An iterative approach to designing learning experiences*. Routledge.
- Chan, C. K. Y. (2023). Assessment for experiential learning, 379.
- Chan, H. H. K., Kwong, H. Y. C., Shu, G. L. F., Ting, C. Y., & Lai, F. H. Y. (2021). Effects of experiential learning programmes on adolescent prosocial behaviour, empathy, and subjective well-being: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 709699. <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/psychology/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.709699/full>
- Coker, J. S., Heiser, E., Taylor, L., & Book, C. (2019). Impacts of experiential learning depth and breadth on student outcomes. *Journal of Experiential Education*, 40(1), 5–23. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/1053825916678265>
- Corpuz, B. B., & Salandanan, G. G. (2020). *Principles and strategies of teaching*. Lorimar Publishing.
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches (5th ed.)* Sage publications.
- Elamin, A. (2019). Gender disparities in education and the influence on girls' educational interest in the arab world. *Journal of International Women's Studies*, 20(2), 55–68.

- Eppard, J., Kaviani, A., Bowles, M., & Johnson, J. (2021). Edtech cultururation: Integrating a culturally relevant pedagogy into educational technology. *Electronic Journal of e-Learning*, 19(6), 516–530.
- Falloon, G. (2019). Using simulations to teach young students science concepts: An experiential learning theoretical analysis. *Computers & Education*, 135, 138–159. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S036013151930051X>
- Febriyanti, N. K. S., & Putra, M. (2020). Mathematics learning interest of elementary school students in using metaphorical thinking learning model. *Journal of Education Technology*, 4(3), 273–278.
- Gezim, B. A. R. A., & Xhomara, N. (2020). The effect of student-centered teaching and problem-based learning on academic achievement in science. *Journal of Turkish Science Education*, 17(2), 180–199. <https://www.tused.org/index.php/tused/article/view/970>
- Irons, A., & Elkington, S. (2021). *Enhancing learning through formative assessment and feedback*. Routledge.
- Karimi, M. N., & Hosseini Zade, S. S. (2019). Teachers’ use of motivational strategies: Effects of a motivation-oriented professional development course. *Innovation in Language Learning and Teaching*, 13(2), 194–204.
- Khasawneh, M. (2024a). Beyond digital platforms: Gamified skill development in real-world scenarios and environmental variables. *International Journal of Data and Network Science*, 8(1), 213–220.
- Khasawneh, M. (2024b). Beyond digital platforms: Gamified skill development in real-world scenarios and environmental variables. *International Journal of Data and Network Science*, 8(1), 213–220.
- Ledger, S., Ersozlu, Z., & Fischetti, J. (2019). Preservice teachers’ confidence and preferred teaching strategies using teachlive™ virtual learning environment: A two-step cluster analysis. *Journal Name, volume number, page range*.
- Lena, M. S., Trisno, E., & Khairat, F. (2022). The effect of motivation and interest on students’ english learning outcomes. *Mextesol Journal*, 46(3), n3. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/02635143.2018.1489789>
- Li, J., & Zhou, Y. (2019). The impacts of the exam-oriented education system on chinese students’ psychological well-being and learning interest. *Educational Review*, 71(5), 564–580.
- Liu, X., & Moeller, A. J. (2019). Promoting learner engagement through interactive digital tools. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/teachlearnfacpub/310/>
- Madkins, T. C., & McKinney de Royston, M. (2019). Illuminating political clarity in culturally relevant science instruction. *Science Education*, 103(6), 1319–1346.
- McCombes, S. (2019). Descriptive research. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/descriptive-research>
- Mohd Shahali, E. H., Halim, L., Rasul, M. S., Osman, K., & Mohamad Arsad, N. (2019). Students’ interest towards stem: A longitudinal study. *Research in Science & Technological Education*, 37(1), 71–89.
- Morley, D. A., & Jamil, M. G. (2021). *Introduction: Real world learning—recalibrating the higher education response towards application to lifelong learning and diverse career paths*.

- Muir, T., Wang, I., Trimble, A., Mainsbridge, C., & Douglas, T. (2022). Using interactive online pedagogical approaches to promote student engagement. *Education Sciences*, 12(6), 415. <https://www.mdpi.com/2227-7102/12/6/415>
- Nascimbeni, F., & Burgos, D. (2019). Unveiling the relationship between the use of open educational resources and the adoption of open teaching practices in higher education. *Sustainability*, 11(20), 5637.
- Nichols, S. L., & Berliner, D. C. (2019). The negative impact of high-stakes testing on student motivation and learning. *Journal of Education Policy*, 34(4), 482–502.
- Pangilinan, A. (2019). Addressing the resource gaps in philippine education. *Journal of Educational Innovation*, 5(1), 45–58.
- Prasetyo, J. H., & Riyanto, S. (2019). The effect of emotional intelligence, learning interest, and discipline on students' learning outcomes in smp negeri 141 jakarta. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, 4(5), 973–980.
- Privitera, G. J. (2020). *Research methods for the behavioral sciences (3rd ed.)* Sage Publications.
- Priyakanth, R., Abburi, R., & Praveena, M. (2021). Design and impact of interactive video content for the improvement of student engagement and learning. *Journal of Engineering Education Transformations*, 34, 518. <https://sciresol.s3.us-east-2.amazonaws.com/srs-j/jeet/pdf/volume34/specialissue/JEET639.pdf>
- Quigley, C. F., & Herro, D. (2019). *An educator's guide to steam: Engaging students using real-world problems*. Teachers College Press.
- Qureshi, M. A., Khaskheli, A., Qureshi, J. A., Raza, S. A., & Yousufi, S. Q. (2023). Factors affecting students' learning performance through collaborative learning and engagement. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 31(4), 2371–2391.
- Raman, A., Thannimalai, R., & Ismail, S. N. (2019). Principals' technology leadership and its effect on teachers' technology integration in 21st century classrooms. *International Journal of Instruction*, 12(4), 423–442.
- Raygan, A., & Moradkhani, S. (2022). Factors influencing technology integration in an efl context: Investigating efl teachers' attitudes, tpack level, and educational climate. *Computer Assisted Language Learning*, 35(8), 1789–1810.
- Reardon, S. F. (2019). The widening academic achievement gap between the rich and the poor: New evidence and possible explanations. In *Whither opportunity? rising inequality and the uncertain life chances of low-income children* (pp. 91–116). Russell Sage Foundation.
- Safapour, E., Kermanshachi, S., & Taneja, P. (2019). A review of nontraditional teaching methods: Flipped classroom, gamification, case study, self-learning, and social media. *Education Sciences*, 9(4), 273. <https://www.mdpi.com/2227-7102/9/4/273>
- Salandanan, G. G. (2020). *Teaching strategies for the modern classroom*. Phoenix Publishing House.
- Shemshack, A., Kinshuk, & Spector, J. M. (2021). A comprehensive analysis of personalized learning components. *Journal of Computers in Education*, 8(4), 485–503.
- Shofwan, I., Aminatun, S., Handoyo, E., & Kariadi, M. T. (2021). The effect of e-learning on students' learning interest in the equivalence education program. *Journal of Nonformal Education*, 7(1), 103–111.
- Stoten, D. W. (2020). Practical heutagogy: Promoting personalized learning in management education. *Adult Learning*, 31(4), 161–174.

- Sugden, N., Brunton, R., MacDonald, J., Yeo, M., & Hicks, B. (2021). Evaluating student engagement and deep learning in interactive online psychology learning activities. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 37(2), 45–65. <https://ajet.org.au/index.php/AJET/article/view/6632>
- Sutarto, S., Sari, D. P., & Fathurrochman, I. (2020). Teacher strategies in online learning to increase students' interest in learning during covid-19 pandemic. *Jurnal Konseling Dan Pendidikan*, 8(3), 129–137.
- Tang, Y., Ding, D., Rao, Y., Zheng, Y., Zhang, D., Zhao, L., & Zhou, J. (2019). Coin: A large-scale dataset for comprehensive instructional video analysis. *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 1207–1216. https://openaccess.thecvf.com/content_CVPR_2019/html/Tang_COIN_A_Large-Scale_Dataset_for_Comprehensive_Instructional_Video_Analysis_CVPR_2019_paper.html
- Toba, R., Noor, W. N., & Sanu, L. O. (2019). The current issues of indonesian efl students' writing skills: Ability, problem, and reason in writing comparison and contrast essay. *Dinamika Ilmu*, 19(1), 57–73. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1217811>
- Toropova, A., Johansson, S., & Myrberg, E. (2019). The role of teacher characteristics for student achievement in mathematics and student perceptions of instructional quality. *Education Inquiry*, 10(4), 275–299.
- Uiboleht, K., Karm, M., & Postareff, L. (2019). Relations between students' perceptions of the teaching-learning environment and teachers' approaches to teaching: A qualitative study. *Journal of Further and Higher Education*, 43(10), 1456–1475. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/0309877X.2018.1491958>
- Ullah, A., & Anwar, S. (2020). The effective use of information technology and interactive activities to improve learner engagement. *Education Sciences*, 10(12), 349. <https://www.mdpi.com/2227-7102/10/12/349>
- Walkington, C., & Bernacki, M. L. (2020). Appraising research on personalized learning: Definitions, theoretical alignment, advancements, and future directions. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 52(3), 235–252.
- Widiastuti, I. A. M. S., Mukminatien, N., Prayogo, J. A., & Irawati, E. (2020). Dissonances between teachers' beliefs and practices of formative assessment in efl classes. *International Journal of Instruction*, 13(1), 71–84.
- Wijaya, H., Darmawan, I. P. A., Setiana, S. C., Helaluddin, H., & Weismann, I. T. J. (2021). Active reconnecting learning strategies to increase student interest and active learning. *Indonesian Journal of Instructional Media and Model*, 3(1), 26–37. <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/98fb/b7f90b5b9df12514341c3991e5c255d422bb.pdf>
- Xuan, Q., Cheung, A., & Sun, D. (2022). The effectiveness of formative assessment for enhancing reading achievement in k-12 classrooms: A meta-analysis. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 990196.
- Yilmaz, A. (2021). The effect of technology integration in education on prospective teachers' critical and creative thinking, multidimensional 21st century skills and academic achievements. *Participatory Educational Research*, 8(2), 163–199.
- Yurtseven Avci, Z., O'Dwyer, L. M., & Lawson, J. (2020). Designing effective professional development for technology integration in schools. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 36(2), 160–177.

- Yusupova, N., Skudareva, G., & Milkevich, O. (2019). The socio-cultural meanings of the new pedagogical education. *ARPHA Proceedings, 1*, 1027–1037.
- Zainuddin, Z., Shujahat, M., Haruna, H., & Chu, S. K. W. (2020). The role of gamified e-quizzes on student learning and engagement: An interactive gamification solution for a formative assessment system. *Computers Education, 145*, 103729.
- Zhai, X., Zhang, M., Li, M., & Zhang, X. (2019). Understanding the relationship between levels of mobile technology use in high school physics classrooms and the learning outcome. *British Journal of Educational Technology, 50*(2), 750–766.